

A feasibility study on using a simplified mass balance to predict potassium in integrated freshwater aquaculture

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed whether simplified mass balance calculations that neglect retention could be used to predict the concentration of potassium (hypothesis: yes) and phosphorus (hypothesis: no) in aquaculture systems, irrespective of feed ingredient choice. Three feeds with distinct formulations and graded levels of potassium and phosphorus were fed to Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) in recirculating aquaculture systems. All inputs (feed, water, caustic) and outputs (water, sludge, fish) were recorded throughout the 91-day experiment. Mass balance calculations with and without retention term (fish, sludge) were then used for prediction. The steady state concentration based on a simplified mass balance was systematically about 20 % lower than predicted. No unambiguous statement could be made about phosphorus due to unaccounted inputs that led to considerable deviation of observed from predicted concentrations. The results of this study indicate that the simplified mass balance might be appropriate to estimate potassium concentrations. Additional studies are, however, necessary to validate the outcomes for a wider range of feed ingredients and fish species.

1. Introduction

Integrated aquaculture involves the combination of aquaculture farming with other agricultural practices to create synergies. Coupling aquaculture with a complementary system such as hydroponics, for instance, reduces nutrient losses and substantially improves resource-use efficiency through additional yield. Such aquaponic systems offer a promising way to reduce the environmental impact of food production in comparison with stand-alone aquaculture or hydroponics (Greenfeld et al., 2022). However, aquaculture can be integrated with a wide variety of plants and production systems beyond edible crops and hydroponics, including ornamental and medicinal species, and constructed wetlands.

The effectiveness of integrated systems depends ultimately on the quantity and the ratios of available nutrients. Nutritional imbalances have been described as a major issue in aquaponics (Bittsánszky et al.,

2016), limiting nutrient uptake efficiency and constraining productivity. Two key plant nutrients that are often deficient in aquaponics are phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) (Bittsánszky et al., 2016, Lunda et al., 2019, Tůmová et al., 2025). The input of P and K into aquaculture systems is controlled by their levels in fish feed (Sugiura, 2018, Tellbüscher et al., 2025a). A strategy to address these deficiencies is thus the use of specialized feed formulations that supply higher levels of target nutrients. Such an approach could support system performance without requiring system operators to intervene through the addition of fertilizer (Robaina et al., 2019).

Past studies related to tailored aquaponics feeds assessed whether elevated K mass fractions in the feed affect fish growth performance (Siqwepu et al., 2020) and additionally translate into higher plant growth (Duarte and Cerozi, 2024). Another line of research assessed the excretion of K and P, among other plant nutrients, in response to the choice of feed ingredients (Pinho et al., 2024; Gebauer et al., 2023, Shaw

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et al., 2022, Shaw et al., 2024). It is known that the extent of P excretion is influenced by the digestibility of the respective feed ingredient and the total mass fraction of P in the diet (Sugiura, 2018). The excreted P will not necessarily be recovered from the water, because chemical interactions can limit its solubility (Cerozi and Fitzsimmons, 2017, Tellbüscher et al., 2024). There is, however, a takeaway related to K from the studies conducted on aquaponic feeds: Those studies that a) ran over several weeks and b) did not include plants in their experimental setup is that the K concentrations in solution appear to be proportional to the mass fraction in feed (S1). This is plausible, as virtually all known K salts are highly soluble in water (Rumble, 2019). In addition, this observation indicates that it might be possible to predict the concentration of K mathematically, based on the mass balance.

Mass balance models make use of the fact that the inputs, outputs, and transformations of nutrients within a system follow the law of mass conservation. Ergo, the mass of the outputs must equal the mass of the inputs. This makes the mass balance a powerful tool for estimating the accumulation or depletion of specific elements, based on known inputs and system parameters. Closed aquaponic systems, or the recirculating aquaculture sub-system (RAS) in on-demand coupled systems, can be simplified as continuous flow stirred tank reactors (CSTR). The characteristics of CSTR are continuous flow and perfect mixing (Fogler, 2016). While mass balance calculations can account for additional constraints such as solubility limits and precipitation reactions, doing so requires data that may be unavailable or impractical to obtain. Consequently, such approaches are often less applicable in routine or operational settings. However, highly precise predictions may not be necessary if the deviation from ideal models can be estimated or bounded.

Based on the provided background, this study tested the hypothesis that K concentrations resulting from feeding a model species with three different diets could be predicted by simplified mass balance calculations, irrespective of the feed ingredient choice. In contrast, P was expected to deviate from such predictions due to its varying bioavailability and constrained solubility in water. The simplification was to ignore retention, which reduces the demand for data considerably. Fish growth was evaluated to assess whether the chosen feed formulations were of commercial relevance.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Ethical approval

All experimental procedures involving animals were approved by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic. The project was conducted at the University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice under the Ministry of Agriculture's permit 45048/2020-MZE-18134.

2.2. Experimental diets

Three experimental diets (control, PK+, PK++) containing graded levels of potassium and phosphorus were formulated. Feed production was conducted by a commercial feed manufacturer (Nutrin s.r.o, Hradec Králové, Czech Republic). The exact formulation, and proximate, phosphorus, and potassium analysis results are shown in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. The control feed resembled a diet for Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) as it is commercially available. The PK+ and PK++ feeds were formulated by using predominantly natural feed ingredients that would result in gradually increased P and K mass fractions. KH_2PO_4 was added as an inorganic source of P and K, contributing 10% and 8% of the total P, and 4% and 3% of the total K in the PK+ (+7.1 g kg⁻¹ P, +2.6 g kg⁻¹ K) and PK++ (+11.7 g kg⁻¹ P, +6.4 g kg⁻¹ K) feed, respectively, in comparison with the control. In addition, ingredients for the PK+ feed were chosen based on the replacement of fishmeal by alternative (mostly plant-based) protein sources, while the PK++ diet was formulated following a circular

Table 1

Raw material formulation of experimental feeds for *Oreochromis niloticus*. The control feed resembles a commercial feed. The PK+ feed uses fishmeal alternatives, while the PK++ feed was formulated based on regionally available feed ingredients.

Ingredient	Treatment		
	control	PK+	PK++
Marine fish meal, LT 72 %*	20.6	-	-
Freshwater fish meal ^{*,†}	-	20.0	10.0
Insect meal ^{*,‡}	-	-	17.4
Soybean meal, SOPRO-TG	25.6	-	-
Soy protein concentrate, SPC75	4.0	-	-
Wheat gluten*	-	2.1	-
Pea protein concentrate*	-	8.2	-
Faba bean protein, E1065X	-	7.6	-
Spirulina*	-	14.8	9.7
Feather meal, 85 NL*	11.2	-	-
Brewer's yeast, MrazAgro*	-	16.2	18.0
Casein*	-	2.0	2.0
Poultry meal	-	-	15.8
Sunflower protein	-	-	5.3
Rapeseed oil cake	-	-	3.9
Rapeseed oil	6.3	4.6	1.4
Wheat flour*	30.3	5.4	1.6
Corn starch*	-	15.1	11.0
Vitamin + mineral premix	2.0	2.0	2.0
KH_2PO_4	-	2.0	2.0

[†] consisting of Common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*) and Channel catfish (*Ictalurus punctatus*).

[‡] consisting of Black soldier fly (*Hermetia illucens*).

* produced in Czech Republic.

Table 2

Nutritional composition of experimental feeds. Analyses were conducted by EKO-LAB s.r.o., Zamberk, Czechia. Results refer to the feed as fed (wet weight).

Parameter	Treatment		
	control	PK+	PK++
Dry matter (g kg ⁻¹)	955.4	917.0	937.2
Crude protein (g kg ⁻¹)	387.8	412.5	437.5
Crude fat (g kg ⁻¹)	63.6	46.2	54.3
Ash (g kg ⁻¹)	58.5	84.8	104.2
P (g kg ⁻¹)	6.9	14.0	18.6
K (g kg ⁻¹)	10.5	13.1	16.9

approach, using regionally available (pronouncedly animal-based) feed ingredients. More information on the formulation of the feeds is provided elsewhere (Roy et al., 2025), while the sources of the feed ingredients are specified in the supplementary material (S2). It was attempted for all feeds to keep the crude protein and crude fat content of the three feeds as comparable as possible to ensure that the growth of the experimental fish might not be affected by those nutrients. The feed formulation considered lysine requirements for *O. niloticus* with an average inclusion rate of 2.4%, which is above the reported requirement for optimum growth of about 1.6% of total protein (Diógenes et al., 2016, do Nascimento et al., 2020).

2.3. Experimental system

The experiment was conducted in three independent RAS ($V_{\text{system}} = 5800$ L) with a total surface area of 8.2 m², out of which 4.1 m² were covered with Styrofoam (biofilter) to reduce evaporation losses. The general setup is depicted in Fig. 1.

Each system consisted of four circular rearing tanks ($V_{\text{tank}} = 630$ L) made from black polypropylene of which one was kept empty during the experiment. Each tank was equipped with a bottom drain and an overflow. Disk aerators were placed in each tank and supplied by an air pump (JDK-S 300, 300 L min⁻¹, Secoh Shanghai LTD, Shanghai, China) to ensure sufficient oxygenation of the rearing water. Overflow water

Fig. 1. Schematic depiction of the experimental system. Blue arrows indicate water flows, while brown arrows indicate sludge flows within the system. Created in BioRender. Tellbüscher, A. (2025) <https://BioRender.com/08fpi3a>.

from the rearing tanks passed through a drum filter (ECO 15, DVS Filtertechnik, Kerkrade, Netherlands) where particles were removed. The clean water was then collected in a retention tank ($V_{sump} = 750$ L), while the backwash water from the drum filter was collected in a sedimentation cone ($V_{vortex} = 70$ L) where particles were allowed to settle. The particle-free supernatant eventually flowed back into the retention tank. The retention tank water was pumped through a heating element (T03, 3 kW, Electro Engineering LTD, Hertfordshire, United Kingdom) and into a moving bed filter (MBF; $V_{bio} = 2500$ L). The water flow was set to approximately $10 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ using a recirculation pump (DCP 20000, Jebao Co. LTD, Guangdong, China). After passing the MBF, the water flowed back into the rearing tanks by gravity.

2.4. Experimental procedure

Each system was stocked with 690 juvenile mixed-sex Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) with an initial bodyweight (BW) of 140.7 ± 32.0 g, resulting in a stocking density of 15.4 kg m^{-3} . Fish were divided into three tanks per RAS. All RAS were operated under a light-dark regime of 12 h:12 h. The experiment lasted for a total of 91 days.

During the experiment, fish were fed three times a day at an average feeding rate of $2.5 \% \text{ d}^{-1} \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ BW}$. Uneaten pellets were counted. The feed refusal was then calculated based on the average weight per pellet that was determined by weighing approximately 1 g of each feed and dividing the weight by the number of pellets. Feed rations were adjusted monthly according to the biomass determined during interim weighing.

A water temperature of 25.5°C , pH around 7.0, and oxygen saturation above 80 % were targeted in the RAS. The water parameters were measured daily using a multimeter probe (HI98494, Hanna Instruments Czech s.r.o., Prague, Czech Republic). The pH was maintained around 7.0 by daily addition of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ to the retention tank and noting down the exact mass of the added caustic. Also, freshwater was added daily to the system at $3.8 \% \text{ d}^{-1}$ of the system volume ($V_{ex} = 220$ L) to top up the water loss through the backwash water of the drum filter, flushing of the bottom drains, and evaporation. The top-up water was a mixture of tap water and rainwater.

2.5. Sampling

System water samples (15 mL) were taken bi-weekly from a randomly chosen rearing tank. The samples were immediately filtered through a cellulose acetate filter (Rotilabo, $\text{Ø} = 25$ mm, pore size $0.45 \mu\text{m}$, Carl Roth, Karlsruhe, Germany), acidified with $100 \mu\text{L}$ HCl (2 M) and stored in centrifuge tubes at 4°C .

Bi-weekly solids samplings took place by collecting the water from the bottom drains and drum filter backwash, unifying it in a 200 L plastic tub and determining the total weight of the sample. The volume of the sludge-water mix was then calculated with an assumed density of 1.0 kg L^{-1} . It was furthermore assumed that the average volume of the sludge-water mix determined throughout the experiment would correspond with the volume of water removed every day. Evaporation losses and suspended solids were neglected. The sludge-water mix in the plastic tub was aerated to homogenize the sample. Then, the total solid (TS) content was determined by filling pre-weighed aluminum boats in triplicate with sludge-water mix, subsequent weighing using a precision scale (Adventurer Pro, Ohaus GmbH, Nänikon, Switzerland) for determination of the sample volume and evaporation of the water at 105°C until mass constancy was reached.

Sludge samples for element analysis were obtained by letting sludge-water mix settle in Imhoff cones, pouring off the supernatant and transferring the remaining sludge into 500 mL plastic sample containers. Samples were stored at 4°C .

Feed samples were taken by monthly sampling of 100 g of each diet from the feed bags. Samples were unified per diet and stored at 4°C .

The average initial bodyweight of the fish was determined by individually weighing 30 randomly selected fish after anesthesia with clove oil. To determine the body composition at the beginning of the experiment, five fish were randomly selected, killed with a blow to the head and bleeding out by cutting the gill arches, pooled and stored at -20°C until further processing. On the last day of the experiment, the final weight of each fish was determined individually, and its sex was determined by assessing the genital pore. During the final weighing, two fish (one male, one female) per tank (in total six fish per system) were randomly selected, and underwent the same process as described for the initial fish sampling.

2.6. Sample processing and analysis

Fish samples were freeze-dried (LC 2–4, Christ, Werningerode, Germany) and homogenized using a kitchen mixer. Sludge samples were thawed and all contaminations (uneaten feed pellets etc.) manually removed. Samples were eventually transferred into aluminum trays and dried at 105°C until constant weight was reached. Feed samples were dried accordingly as well. Dry samples were eventually finely ground.

Approximately 0.25 g of each ground sample was weighed, mixed with 10 mL HNO_3 (63 %, Suprapure®, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany), and digested for 35 min using a closed microwave reaction system (MARS® 5, CEM Corporation, Matthews, NC, USA) with a power rate of 650 W. Digestates were transferred to 50 mL volumetric flasks and filled up with ultrapure water (Simplicity® system, Millipore SAS, Molsheim, France). Samples were transferred to 15 mL centrifuge tubes and stored at 4°C .

Proximate analyses of feed samples were done by an external laboratory (EKO-LAB, spol. s.r.o., Zamberk, Czechia). The nitrogen content of the fish samples was determined in-house by Kjeldahl analysis. The ammonium, nitrite, nitrate and soluble reactive phosphorus content of the water samples was determined by continuous flow analysis (CFA; FSR Seal High-Resolution AA3 chemical analyzer, Seal Analytical, Norderstedt, Germany). The element composition of the water, fish, and sludge samples was determined using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES; iCAP 7400 ICP-OES, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). CFA and ICP-OES analyses were conducted in the laboratories of the Leibniz Institute for Freshwater Ecology

and Inland Fisheries, Berlin, Germany.

2.7. Calculations and statistics

All calculations and statistical analyses were conducted with R v4.5.0 (R Core Team, 2021) at a significance level of 5 %. The growth and feed metrics were calculated using the *aquacultuR* package v0.0.9 (Tellbüscher et al., 2025b). The male-female counts between treatments were compared with a Chi-Squared test. Groupwise comparisons of metric data between treatments were conducted by multiple contrast testing.

The inputs of x into the system originate from the makeup water to top up evaporated water, drumfilter backwash water, and tank bottom drains, the fish feed, and chemicals added to increase the pH and alkalinity. These can be summarized as a composite concentration $c_{in,x}^*$ by dividing through the daily water flow Q_{in} .

$$c_{in,x}^* = \frac{\dot{m}_{water.in,x} + \dot{m}_{feed,x} + \dot{m}_{alkalinity,x}}{Q_{in}} = c_{water.in,x} + \frac{\dot{m}_{feed,x} + \dot{m}_{alkalinity,x}}{Q_{in}} \quad (1)$$

The input of x via the feed ($\dot{m}_{feed,x}$) and alkalinity ($\dot{m}_{alkalinity,x}$) can be calculated as the total dry weight of the feed fed throughout the experiment (\dot{m}_{feed}) or the alkalinity compound added to the system ($\dot{m}_{alkalinity}$) multiplied by the mass fraction of x in the feed ($\omega_{feed,x}$) or the alkalinity compound ($\omega_{alkalinity,x}$), respectively.

$$\dot{m}_{feed,x} = \dot{m}_{feed}\omega_{feed,x} \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{m}_{alkalinity,x} = \dot{m}_{alkalinity}\omega_{alkalinity,x} \quad (3)$$

The volume flow of water entering the system was determined as the sum of the empirically determined sludge outflow and the calculated evaporation rate Q_{evap} .

$$Q_{in} = Q_{out} + Q_{evap} \quad (4)$$

Q_{evap} was estimated with the Empirical Mass Transfer Equation according to Dalton (McMahon et al., 2016)

$$Q_{evap} = (25 + 19v) A (p_s^* - p_a) \quad (5)$$

where A is the water surface area in m^2 , p_s^* is the saturation vapor pressure at the evaporating surface temperature, p_a is the current vapor pressure of the air, and v is the wind speed (assumed to be 0.1 m s^{-1}).

The removal of x via the outflow takes place both in form of particulate sludge and in dissolved form via the outflow water. This sludge–water mixture is removed from the system via the bottom drain and drum filter backwash. Its volumetric flow (Q_{out}) was determined indirectly by weighing the total mass of sludge–water mixture (m_{mix}) removed during the sampling events and converting it to volume using the density of the mixture (ρ_{mix}). Assuming a density of 1000 g L^{-1} , the average sludge flow rate was calculated as the arithmetic mean of the flow rates for each sampling day according to:

$$Q_{out} = \frac{1}{t} \sum_i \frac{m_{mix,i}}{\rho_{mix}} \quad (6)$$

The sludge dry matter was calculated as follows:

$$\omega_{sludge} = \frac{m_{dry} - m_{boat}}{m_{sample} - m_{boat}} \quad (7)$$

where m_{boat} is the weight of an empty weighing boat, m_{dry} is the dry weight of the weighing boat after drying a sludge sample, and m_{sample} is the mass of the initial sample in the weighing boat.

Additional removal of component x from the water phase takes place through incorporation into fish biomass. Fish growth during the experiment was linear (data not shown). Accordingly, the average uptake rate of component x into fish biomass is given by

$$\dot{m}_{fish,x} = \frac{\Delta m_{fish}}{t} \omega_{fish,x} \quad (8)$$

where Δm_{fish} denotes the total fish biomass gain over the experimental period t , and $\omega_{fish,x}$ is the mass fraction of component x in fish biomass.

The mass balance for the system can be written as

$$V \frac{dc_x}{dt} = c_{in,x}^* Q_{in} - c_x Q_{out} - Q_{out} \gamma_{sludge} \omega_{sludge,x} - \dot{m}_{fish,x} \quad (9)$$

with the lefthand side denoting the mass change of x in the system volume, $c_{in,x}^* Q_{in}$ denoting the sum of the inputs expressed as composite concentration, $c_x Q_{out}$ denoting the advective removal of x with the water phase and $Q_{out} \gamma_{sludge} \omega_{sludge,x}$ with the solid phase of the sludge stream, and $\dot{m}_{fish,x}$ being the retention of x in fish biomass. The mass balance expression can eventually be integrated and yields

$$c_x(t) = c_{ss} + (c_0 - c_{ss}) e^{-\frac{Q_{in}}{V} t} \quad (10)$$

with c_0 being the initial concentration of x , and where

$$c_{ss} = \frac{Q_{in} c_{in,x}^*}{Q_{out}} - \gamma_{sludge} \omega_{sludge,x} - \frac{\dot{m}_{fish,x}}{Q_{out}} \quad (11)$$

analogous to the CSTR equation. All volumes and volume flows are given in L and $L d^{-1}$, all masses in g, time in d, mass concentrations in $mg L^{-1}$, and mass fractions in $mg g^{-1}$.

The CSTR model was fitted to the measured concentration data with the *optim()* function from the *Metrics* package v0.1.4 (Hammer and Frasco, 2012). The full mass balance considered all introduced terms, while the simplified mass balance neglected nutrient retention through fish and sludge, simplifying the equation to

$$c_x(t) = \frac{Q_{in} c_{in,x}^*}{Q_{out}} + (c_0 - \frac{Q_{in} c_{in,x}^*}{Q_{out}}) e^{-\frac{Q_{in}}{V} t} \quad (12)$$

In cases where the systems have been optimized for low evaporation, evaporation losses may also be neglected. This further simplifies Eq. 12 as follows.

$$c_x(t) = c_{in,x}^* + (c_0 - c_{in,x}^*) e^{-t \frac{Q_{in}}{V}} \quad (13)$$

The uncertainty of the retention terms was estimated by error propagation.

3. Results and discussion

The key hypotheses of the present study were that the concentrations and overall dynamics of K would be determined by the sole K input into the system, regardless of the choice of specific feed ingredients, while dissolved P would be controlled by its bioavailability and finally, the saturation concentration at chemical equilibrium. It was furthermore assumed that growth and feed conversion would not be affected by the choice of feed ingredients, as long as they are not too uncommonly used in conventional aquaculture feeds.

3.1. Potassium and phosphorus dynamics

Prediction results based on mass balance calculations and observed concentrations of K and P are shown in Figs. 2 and 3. Note that the difference between optimized fit and the complete mass balance is the mass balance error. It was further assumed that the difference between the complete and simplified mass balances is comparable across systems, provided that the material dynamics are independent of feed composition and substance retention in biomass and sludge, and therefore do not influence the substance concentration within the system.

Overall, the concentration of K over time developed closely to the complete mass balance prediction. Differences in the final concentration of K can be ascribed to differences in the retention of dietary K by fish,

Fig. 2. Observed and predicted potassium (K) concentrations in recirculating aquaculture systems stocked with *O. niloticus* and fed with experimental feeds with graded levels of K and P ($t = 91$ d). Initial differences in K concentrations reflect pre-existing variability unrelated to experimental feeds. Black dots indicate measured data, while lines depict predicted concentrations. Dashed lines: predictions considering nutrient retention in fish and sludge. Dotted lines: predictions without considering nutrient retention. Highlighted areas: prediction error, based on the mass estimation error of bound K. Vertical dashed lines: 0x, 1x, 2x, and 3x HRT.

Fig. 3. Observed and predicted phosphorus (P) and calcium (Ca) concentrations in recirculating aquaculture systems stocked with *O. niloticus* and fed with experimental feeds with graded levels of K and P during the experiment ($t = 91$ d). Initial differences in P and Ca concentrations reflect pre-existing variability unrelated to experimental feeds. Black dots indicate measured data, while lines depict predicted concentrations. Dashed lines: predictions considering nutrient retention in fish and sludge. Dotted lines: prediction without considering nutrient retention. Highlighted area: prediction error, based on the estimated error of the mass of bound P and Ca. Vertical dashed lines: 0x, 1x, 2x, and 3x HRT.

which was highest in the PK+ treatment (13.5 %), followed by the control (9.4 %) and the PK++ treatment (4.7 %). The mass fraction of K in the tissue was, analogously, highest in the PK+ treatment at the end of the experiment (14.1 mg g^{-1}). The control (9.3 mg g^{-1}) and PK++ treatment (10.1 mg g^{-1}) were, meanwhile, similar. Changes in the K mass fraction in the body of *O. niloticus* in response to different dietary levels have not been described in the scientific literature to the best of the authors' knowledge and might be a result of the differences in diet composition (high amount of legumes in the PK+ treatment).

Based on the Mean Absolute Error (MAE), dissolved K was underestimated by $6.5 \% \pm 1.4 \%$ in comparison with the best fit when accounting for the K bound in sludge and fish biomass in addition to the K inputs in the calculation. The smallest deviation was observed in the PK++ treatment ($-0.3 \% \pm 1.1 \%$), which can be considered as not distinguishable from the observed concentrations as they lie within the estimated error band of the prediction. This was followed by the control ($-6.8 \% \pm 1.7 \%$) and the PK+ treatment ($-12.3 \% \pm 1.4 \%$). Mass balance errors occur due to unaccounted inputs or outputs or an error in the estimation. In the current study, feed was the major input route of K into the system, while fish and sludge equally contribute to its retention (Fig. 4). The observed differences might thus originate from the random error of feed analysis or leached K from uneaten feed. However, the mass balance error in this study is low in comparison with errors between 39 % and 80 % that were reported for K mass balances in other studies (Delaide et al., 2017, Strauch et al., 2018).

A high initial K concentration, followed by a concentration decrease by about 50 % over time was observed in the control and PK+ treatment. This was only recognized in retrospect, since all samples were analyzed after the experiment had ended. However, the observed concentration decrease was captured by the prediction, verifying the feasibility of the chosen mass balance approach. An explanation for the discrepancy between the initial and the expected K concentration (2.8 mg L^{-1} in source water) is likely related to the preparation of the system for this study. While solid deposits were thoroughly removed by brushing and pressure-cleaning from the inner walls of the rearing tanks, the systems were not completely drained but only flushed with

freshwater. However, KOH was regularly used for pH control during the experiment prior to this study (alternating with $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$). This likely led to considerable K accumulation, because an accidental or unrecognized input of more than 300 g of K into the control system appears highly unlikely ($5800 \text{ L} \times [60 \text{ mg L}^{-1} - 2.8 \text{ mg L}^{-1}] \times \text{g} 1000 \text{ mg}^{-1} = 331.76 \text{ g}$). A better system design for such experiments has been described, for instance, in Shaw et al. (2023).

Prior studies have shown that the concentration of K in the system water can be manipulated by means of feed formulation, as can be seen from the trends in dissolved K following the inclusion rates in the used feeds (Duarte and Cerozi, 2024, Shaw et al., 2022, Shaw et al., 2024). This study corroborates these findings and expands them further. A recalculation based on data reported in the mentioned studies yielded results of similar quality when using a simplified mass balance approach (S1).

Simplifying the mass balance by neglecting K bound in fish biomass and sludge would make it easier to implement mass balance calculations in industrial applications. This way, the prediction of substance concentrations would only require knowledge of the nutrient's concentration in the source water and feed. Within a European context, tap water concentrations of K are widely available from the local water suppliers. Feed analyses, meanwhile, can be conducted by certified external laboratories for a relatively low price. Following this approach, it was found that the K concentration was overestimated on average by $19.3 \% \pm 1.4 \%$ in comparison with the complete mass balance. While the differences were similar in the control ($22.3 \% \pm 1.7 \%$) and PK+ treatment ($21.4 \% \pm 1.4 \%$), it was smaller in the PK++ treatment ($14.2 \% \pm 1.1 \%$). Further research is required to confirm that the results obtained do not differ significantly in a statistically sound manner. It might, however, serve as an adequate estimate for many applications to assume that the true concentration of K will be about 80 % of the K predicted by Eq. 10 if Eq. 12 is used instead.

For illustration, if the input of water and feed into an aquaculture system of 1 000 L volume were 50 L d^{-1} and $1 000 \text{ g d}^{-1}$ (500 L kg^{-1} of feed), and the K concentration or inclusion rate 10 mg L^{-1} and 20 mg g^{-1} , respectively, then the daily input would sum up to $50 \text{ L d}^{-1} \times$

Fig. 4. Mass balance of potassium (K) and phosphorus (P) throughout the experiment ($t = 91 \text{ d}$). The alkalinity flow (input of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ to keep pH stable) did not contribute to the input of K and P and is thus not shown.

$10 \text{ mg L}^{-1} + 1000 \text{ g d}^{-1} \times 20 \text{ mg g}^{-1} = 20500 \text{ mg d}^{-1} \text{ K}$. The initial mass of K, given that the system filled with the same water, would be $1000 \text{ L} \times 10 \text{ mg L}^{-1} = 10000 \text{ mg}$. The mass of K in the system after $3\text{HRT} = 3 \times 1000 \text{ L} / 50 \text{ L d}^{-1} = 60 \text{ d}$ would consequently approach $20500 \text{ mg} + (10000 \text{ mg} - 20500 \text{ mg}) \bullet e^{-60 \text{ d} / 20 \text{ d}} \approx 20000 \text{ mg}$, translating to 20 mg L^{-1} . After application of the correction factor, the concentration to be expected would be $20 \text{ mg L}^{-1} \times 0.8$, resulting in a concentration of 16 mg L^{-1} .

As depicted in Fig. 4, the majority of P was recovered in the sludge, analogously to observations from other studies (Shaw et al., 2022, Shaw et al., 2024). Yet, predicting P concentrations based on the mass balance approach failed. As can be seen by the negative values shown in Fig. 3, the observed concentrations were on average $169.0 \% \pm 55.5 \%$ higher than predicted by the complete mass balance. This indicates that an unrecorded source of P contributed to the total input. The differences between treatments were considerable, with the smallest deviation found between the control ($108.9 \% \pm 32.2 \%$) and the PK+ treatment ($123.5 \% \pm 25.0 \%$). Meanwhile, the error for the PK++ treatment was more than twice as high ($274.6 \% \pm 109.4 \%$). The (dimensionless) molar Ca:P ratios of the differences between complete mass balance prediction and fitted curve were 1.9 ± 0.2 , 0.9 ± 0.3 , and 0.6 ± 0.04 for the control, PK+, and PK++ treatment, respectively. Stoichiometric hydroxyapatite (molar formula: $\text{Ca}_{10}(\text{PO}_4)_6(\text{OH})_2$) has a Ca:P ratio of 1.6. As the RAS were in use before the experiment, the unaccounted P input might be explained by dissolution of larger amounts of precipitate that was formed due to the use of $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ to increase the pH during prior experiments. Ergo, it is likely that dissolution of hydroxyapatite contributed to the additional P input. With regards to solubility thresholds, it can furthermore be assumed that the concentration of P in solution was determined by the input of P in the control (Ca:P > 1.6), while being determined by the input of Ca in the PK+ and PK++ treatments (Ca:P < 1.6).

As indicated by the mass balance (Fig. 4), the average difference between the complete and simplified mass balance prediction was $546.6 \% \pm 55.5 \%$ (Fig. 3). The differences between treatments were pronounced, being $354.2 \% \pm 32.2 \%$ in the control, $250.8 \% \pm 25.0 \%$ in the PK+, and $1034.8 \% \pm 109.4 \%$ in the PK++ treatment. This observation can likely be ascribed to differences in the bioavailability and digestibility of P in the respective feeds. P is present in a vast number of inorganic and organic forms, from hydroxyapatite over phospholipids, nucleic acids, to phytic acid in plant-based ingredients (Sugiura, 2018). It was thus expected that no relationship between P input and concentration in solution would be found with a simplified mass balance approach. An additional determinant might have been solubility thresholds. P speciation is strongly pH-dependent (Stumm and Morgan, 1995) and the threshold concentrations under common aquaculture conditions are comparably low (Tellbüscher et al., 2024). However, no solubility calculations were made in this study due to the

Table 3

Feed and growth metrics for Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) after 91 days. IBW: Initial body weight, FBW: Final body weight, AG: Absolute growth, FCR: Feed conversion ratio, TGC: Thermal growth coefficient. Superscript letters indicate significant differences.

Parameter	Treatment		
	control	PK+	PK++
Feed given (kg)	79.425	81.358	75.220
Feed refusal (kg)	2.936	3.745	3.364
Feed intake (kg)	71.101	77.613	70.158
IBW (g)	141 ± 32.1		
FBW (g)	319 ± 114	312 ± 95.4	260 ± 87.1
AG (g)	78.6 ± 1.6	62.4 ± 31.5	58.4 ± 9.1
FCR	1.57 ± 0.16 ^a	1.82 ± 0.12 ^a	2.33 ± 0.22 ^b
TGC	0.75 ± 0.04 ^a	0.74 ± 0.02 ^a	0.55 ± 0.05 ^b
Survival (%)	100	98.3	98.7

large mass balance error and the question whether a solid phase is present or not. Future experiments should be conducted in systems that have been thoroughly cleaned and preferably acid-treated to remove residual P (Table 3).

3.2. Fish rearing, growth, and feed conversion

Rearing parameters are shown in Table 4, while data and some metrics reflecting the growth and feed conversion are shown in Table 3. In the following, significant differences refer to a significance level of 95 % ($p < 0.05$).

Survival in all treatments exceeded > 98 %. The control and PK+ treatment did not significantly differ in growth performance ($p = 0.99$). The total fish biomass in both treatments increased on average by 152.5 g d^{-1} . Meanwhile, the weight increase in the PK++ treatment was significantly lower, reaching 108 g d^{-1} . This pattern was also reflected in the TGC. While the PK+ and control treatments did not significantly differ ($p = 0.70$), the TGC in the PK++ treatment was significantly lower compared with the other two treatments. It is noteworthy that fish in the PK+ treatment had an 11 % higher feed intake (corrected for feed refusal) than the other treatments, while the feed intake of the control and PK++ treatment was almost identical. This led to a (non-significantly; $p = 0.26$) increased FCR in the PK+ treatment compared with the control. The FCR of the PK++ treatment was, meanwhile, significantly elevated; it was 48 % and 28 % higher than in the control and PK+ treatment, respectively. The obtained FCR for the control and PK+ treatments can be considered as (above-)average in comparison with a metadata-based study that found an average FCR between 1.8 and 1.9 at a water temperature of approximately 26°C and dissolved oxygen concentration of about 5 mg L^{-1} , corresponding to the conditions in the present study (Mengistu et al., 2019). The same meta-analysis found an average TGC of 0.9 at the given dissolved oxygen concentration. The TGC of 0.74–0.75 in the control and PK+ treatment of the present study was consequently below average (TGC = 0.86), but the difference might not be significant, as no confidence bands were calculated in the meta-analysis. The TGC of the PK++ treatment, meanwhile, was undoubtedly poor.

In the present study, mixed-sex *O. niloticus* were stocked. It is known that females of *O. niloticus* grow considerably slower than the males due to increased energy expenditures for sexual maturation, production of oocytes, and fasting during mouth breeding (Mair et al., 1995). However, each group consisted of 27 ± 7 males and 49 ± 6 female fish (male:female ratio 0.57 ± 0.19), and no significant differences were found (Chi-Square test: $p = 0.2$). The observed differences in growth and feed conversion are thus likely not related to differences in the male:female ratio between the treatment groups. The rearing parameters were comparable among treatments during the experiment (Table 4). An exception was conductivity, being on average 22 % higher in the PK+ treatment than in the other treatments.

A possible explanation for the lower growth in the PK++ treatment is poor feed performance. The control and PK+ diet both contained about 20 % of fishmeal, while about 50 % of the fishmeal was replaced by insect meal (*Hermetia illucens*) in the PK++ treatment. Higher proportions of insect meal in feed appear to lead to poorer feed conversion and slower growth in larger fish (Rapatsa et al., 2022). This finding is

Table 4

Average abiotic water parameters per treatment (one RAS per treatment) over 91 days.

Parameter	Treatment		
	control	PK+	PK++
Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	25.8 ± 0.8	25.7 ± 0.8	25.2 ± 0.9
pH	6.9 ± 0.1	6.7 ± 0.1	6.8 ± 0.1
O ₂ (% sat.)	79.3 ± 8.0	78.3 ± 7.0	81.7 ± 8.0
Conductivity ($\mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$)	1052.8 ± 92.0	1233.9 ± 69.9	976.4 ± 77.4

thus in line with results from prior studies. One of the reasons appears to be chitin as constituent of insect meal. While *O. niloticus* has limited capacity to digest chitin, higher inclusion rates in the feed cause a reduction in the digestion (Egging et al., 2022).

3.3. Implications for “systemic” feeding

Increasing the K concentration in feed for aquaculture has the potential to render the effluents more suitable for aquaculture systems that integrate plant production. Such systems are, for instance, aquaponics, where the wastewater from an aquaculture system serves as irrigation water for edible plants. K has been described as a plant nutrient that is deficient in wastewater from RAS (Lunda et al., 2019). In addition, it can serve to increase the water purification performance in constructed wetlands, where excess nutrients from aquaculture wastewater are taken up by fast-growing plants as means of end-of-pipe treatment. It has been shown that optimized N:K ratios elevate the reduction efficiency of chemical oxygen demand (COD) and nutrients in constructed wetlands (Bustamante et al., 2011).

Based on the findings of this study, it might be stated as a rule of thumb that 80–90 % of the K input into an aquaculture system will be present in dissolved form. Note that the time after which the concentration will approach the maximum at a constant input rate depends on the hydraulic retention time of the aquaculture system. A good estimate for the point of time when the concentration approaches the maximum is three-times hydraulic retention time (Fogler, 2016). The results of this study should, however, be validated by further studies with other feed formulations. An additional consideration is to use different species to ensure that the observed patterns are also species independent. Follow-up studies should also introduce replicates, as this was not possible in the present study, which limits the generalizability of the presented results.

Considering the high solubility of K in water, the same behavior as found for K might be observable with other compounds such as sodium (Na), that are present in ionic forms. Analogous to K, Na is not bound to other molecules by covalent bonds that would require (enzymatic) cleavage but is present as cation and can thus be excreted in dissolved form. Na can reduce plant growth by causing osmotic stress (Munns and Tester, 2008) and is thus especially problematic in integrated aquaculture systems. The majority of Na appears to enter freshwater aquaculture systems via the feed (unpublished data). Hence, targeted and efficient management of Na in integrated aquaculture systems might be achievable by reducing the mass fraction in feeds according to pre-calculated values. However, more research is required and specific correction factors must be determined for this and other compounds, based on the retention of the respective compound in biomass and sludge.

4. Conclusions

A simplified mass balance that neglects retention terms (biomass, sludge) might be used for the prediction of K. This study suggests that a correction factor of 0.85 may be applied to correct the result for the overestimation from neglecting retention. This study also suggests that the K concentration in solution is independent of the feed ingredients used, but only depends on the K mass fraction. This simple approach might allow for improved management of integrated aquaculture systems without the need for expensive water quality monitoring. However, further studies are required to confirm the presented findings.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ewumi Azeez Folorunso: Investigation. **Hendrik Monsees:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization, Funding acquisition. **Werner Kloas:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Jan Mráz:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration,

Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Anil Axel Tellbüscher:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Radek Gebauer:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Martin Šeda:** Resources, Investigation. **Tobias Goldhammer:** Resources, Investigation. **Koushik Roy:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Ondřej Nikl:** Resources, Investigation.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used Microsoft Copilot in order to write parts of the R code for data analysis and visualization. After using this tool/service, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the publication.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.aquaeng.2026.102691](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaeng.2026.102691).

Data availability

Research data Link Provided

References

- Bittsánszky, A., Uzinger, N., Gyulai, G., Mathis, A., Junge, R., Villarroel, M., Kotzen, B., Kómfives, T., 2016. Nutrient supply of plants in aquaponic systems. *Ecocycles* 2.
- Bustamante, M.A.O., Mier, M.V., Estrada, J.A.E., Domínguez, C.D., 2011. Nitrogen and potassium variation on contaminant removal for a vertical subsurface flow lab scale constructed wetland. *Bioresour. Technol.* 102, 7745–7754.
- Cerozi, B.S., Fitzsimmons, K., 2017. Phosphorus dynamics modeling and mass balance in an aquaponics system. *Agric. Syst.* 153, 94–100.
- R. Core Team, 2021. R: A language and environment for statistical computing.
- Delaide, B., Delhayé, G., Dermience, M., Gott, J., Soyeurt, H., Jijakli, M.H., 2017. Plant and fish production performance, nutrient mass balances, energy and water use of the PAFF Box, a small-scale aquaponic system. *Aquac. Eng.* 78, 130–139.
- Diógenes, A.F., Fernandes, J.B.K., Dorigam, J.C.P., Sakomura, N.K., Rodrigues, F.H.F., Lima, B.T.M., Gonçalves, F.H., 2016. Establishing the optimal essential amino acid

- ratios in juveniles of Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) by the deletion method. *Aquac. Nutr.* 22, 435–443.
- Duarte, S.F.P., Cerozi, B.S., 2024. Enhancing plant growth in aquaponic systems via potassium manipulation in fish feeds: a pilot study of tailored feeds bridging nutritional gaps in aquaponics. *Agric. Syst.* 218.
- Eggink, K.M., Pedersen, P.B., Lund, I., Dalsgaard, J., 2022. Chitin digestibility and intestinal exochitinase activity in Nile tilapia and rainbow trout fed different black soldier fly larvae meal size fractions. *Aquac. Res.* 53, 5536–5546. <https://doi.org/10.1111/are.16035>.
- Fogler, H.S., 2016. Elements of chemical reaction engineering. Prentice-Hall, Boston, 978-1-292-41668-7.
- Gebauer, R., Brüggemann, A., Folorunso, E.A., Goldhammer, T., Gebauer, T., Schöning, V., Bittmann, S., Knopf, K., Mráz, J., Kloas, W., 2023. Species- and diet-specific aquaculture wastewater nutrient profile: implications for aquaponics and development of sustainable aquaponics diet. *Aquaculture* 568.
- Greenfield, A., Becker, N., Bornman, J.F., Spataro, S., Angel, D.L., 2022. Is aquaponics good for the environment?—evaluation of environmental impact through life cycle assessment studies on aquaponics systems. *Aquac. Int.* 30, 305–322.
- Hammer, B., Frasco, M., 2012. Metrics: evaluation metrics for machine learning. CRAN Contrib. Packages.
- Lunda, R., Roy, K., Masilko, J., Mráz, J., 2019. Understanding nutrient throughput of operational RAS farm effluents to support semi-commercial aquaponics: easy upgrade possible beyond controversies. *J. Environ. Manag.* 245, 255–263.
- Mair, G.C., Abucay, J.S., Beardmore, J.A., Skibinski, D.O.F., 1995. Growth performance trials of genetically male tilapia (GMT) derived from YY-males in *Oreochromis niloticus* L.: On station comparisons with mixed sex and sex reversed male populations. *Aquaculture* 137, 313–323. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0044-8486\(95\)01110-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/0044-8486(95)01110-2).
- McMahon, T.A., Finlayson, B.L., Peel, M.C., 2016. Historical developments of models for estimating evaporation using standard meteorological data. *WIREs Water* 3, 788–818.
- Mengistu, S.B., Mulder, H.A., Benzie, J.A.H., Komen, H., 2019. A systematic literature review of the major factors causing yield gap by affecting growth, feed conversion ratio and survival in Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). *Rev. Aquac.* 12, 524–541.
- Munns, R., Tester, M., 2008. Mechanisms of salinity tolerance. *Annu. Rev. Plant Biol.* 59, 651–681.
- do Nascimento, T.M.T., Mansano, C.F.M., Peres, H., Rodrigues, F.H.F., Khan, K.U., Romanelli, R.S., Sakomura, N.K., Fernandes, J.B.K., 2020. Determination of the optimum dietary essential amino acid profile for growing phase of Nile tilapia by deletion method. *Aquaculture* 523.
- Rapatsa, M., Moyo, N., Du, Z.-Y., 2022. A review and meta-analysis of the effects of replacing fishmeal with insect meals on growth of Tilapias and sharptooth catfish. *Aquac. Nutr.* 2022, 1–10.
- Robaina, L., Pirhonen, J., Mente, E., Sánchez, J., Goosen, N., 2019. Fish Diets in Aquaponics. *Aquaponics Food Production Systems*. Springer, Cham, pp. 333–352.
- Roy, K., Bernas, J., Gebauer, R., Tellbüscher, A.A., Nikl, O., Shaw, C., Folorunso, E.A., Kloas, W., Aubin, J., Mráz, J., 2025. Environmental impact assessment of fish feed for aquaponic systems to introduce higher phosphorus and potassium in value-added fish sludge. *Aquaculture* 599, 742142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2025.742142>.
- Rumble, J.R., 2019. CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics, 100th ed. CRC Press, pp. 978–1138367296.
- Pinho, S., Leal, M.M., Shaw, C., Baganz, D., Baganz, G., Staaks, G., Kloas, W., Körner, O., Monsees, H., 2024. Insect-based fish feed in decoupled aquaponic systems: Effect on lettuce production and resource use. *Plos One*. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0295811>.
- Shaw, C., Knopf, K., Kloas, W., 2022. Fish feeds in aquaponics and beyond: a novel concept to evaluate protein sources in diets for circular multitrophic food production systems. *Sustainability* 14.
- Shaw, C., Knopf, K., Klatt, L., Marin Arellano, G., Kloas, W., 2023. Closing nutrient cycles through the use of system-internal resource streams: implications for circular multitrophic food production systems and aquaponic feed development. *Sustainability* 15, 7374–7374.
- Shaw, C., Knopf, K., Roy, K., Ulrichs, C., Kloas, W., 2024. Animal versus plant protein sources in marine ingredient-free aquaponic diets: a case study on nutrient release, and retention of African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) reared in RAS. *Aquaculture* 584.
- Siqwepu, O., Salie, K., Goosen, N., 2020. Evaluation of potassium diformate and potassium chloride in the diet of the African catfish, *Clarias gariepinus* in a recirculating aquaculture system. *Aquaculture* 526.
- Strauch, S.M., Wenzel, L.C., Bischoff, A., Dellwig, O., Klein, J., Schüch, A., Wasenitz, B., Palm, H.W., 2018. Commercial African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) recirculating aquaculture systems: assessment of element and energy pathways with special focus on the phosphorus cycle. *Sustainability* 10.
- Stumm, W., Morgan, J.J., 1995. Aquatic chemistry: Chemical Equilibria and Rates in Natural Waters, 3rd ed. Wiley. 978-0-471-51185-4.
- Sugiura, S.H., 2018. Phosphorus, aquaculture, and the environment. *Rev. Fish. Sci. Aquac.* 26, 515–521.
- Tellbüscher, A.A., Gebauer, R., Mráz, J., 2025a. Nutrients revisited: review and meta-data analysis of nutrient inputs into freshwater aquaculture systems. *Aquaculture* 595.
- Tellbüscher, A.A., van Hullebusch, E., Gebauer, R., Mráz, J., 2024. Assessing the fate and behaviour of plant nutrients in aquaponic systems by chemical equilibrium modelling: a meta-analytical approach. *Water Res.* 264, 122226.
- Tellbüscher, A.A., Karthikeyan M., Machado D.Ce.S., 2025b. aquacultuR: A Comprehensive R Tool for Zootechnical Metrics GitHub.
- Tůmová, V., Benmansour, I., Langhansová, L., Petrýl, M., Bureš, D., Petrová, Š., Haisel, D., Tejnecký, V., Pěchoučková, E., Laloučková, K., Malíková, L., Liška, M., Klouček, P., Monsees, H., 2025. The impact of two aquaponic management strategies (unfertilized and fertilized aquaponics) on the quality and growth of green butterhead lettuce (*Lactuca sativa*, var. Salanova Aquino, Rijk Zwaan). *J. Clean. Prod.* 521, 146202.